

Designing 3D-printed wheat starch cryogels: Effect of geometry on mechanical performance

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ABSTRACT

Cryogels, porous materials obtained by freeze-drying, are used for various food and biomedical applications due to their interesting material properties. The fracture behaviour of 3D-printed cryogel designs as function of structural parameters such as the infill pattern and the number of outer perimeters, was evaluated by performing uniaxial compression with digital image correlation (DIC) analyses. Both structural parameters influence the mechanical performance of the cryogels, with the infill pattern being the dominant factor. A triangular infill pattern with two outer perimeters gave the highest specific modulus, while a rectilinear infill pattern gave the highest energy absorption capacity. Compression tests revealed that a thinner outer wall gave more ductility. To demonstrate potential applications of 3D-printed wheat starch cryogels, we designed and assembled a partially edible glider which showed gliding stability. Our research shows that edible macroporous structures with tuneable mechanical properties can be manufactured by varying the geometrical design through 3D printing. These structures can potentially replace non-edible materials for various applications.

1. Introduction

Design of foods is traditionally centred around sensory properties and nutritional value. These qualities naturally make edible materials both biodegradable and digestible, extending their potential to novel applications such as ‘edible robots’. ‘Edible robots’ could find potential applications in health care (by enabling precise drug delivery and in vivo monitoring of health indicators), environmental management (by reducing waste in farming and facilitating wild animal vaccination), and the promotion of healthier eating habits (by introducing new culinary experiences to consumers) (Floreano et al., 2024).

An edible robot is made up of a main body giving the robot structural and mechanical stability, and specific parts attached to this main body. The selection of the material, its shaping, and its manufacturing process for the robot’s body should align with the intended function. Previously, Kwak et al. developed an edible drone for rescue missions (Kwak et al., 2022). To construct the wings of the edible drone, commercially available puffed rice cookies were laser cut into (half-) hexagonal shapes and connected with edible glue. The results showed that expanded polypropylene materials (EPP) can be replaced by modified rice cookies, without compromising the physical and mechanical properties of the wing. However, the fabrication process of rice-cookie-based wing is not

easily scalable. In addition, commercial rice cookies have restricted physical and mechanical properties, limiting their applicability as a structural material for other edible robot, while the rice cookies still needed to be wrapped in plastic foil. Rice cookies are expanded starch gels created by thermal puffing. The puffing effect depends critically on the moisture content, the thickness of the cookie dough layer, the heating rate, and the moisture diffusion rates. Cryogels are made by freezing a starch suspension, and removing the water by freeze-drying. This is a more flexible and better controlled process, and has already been employed for different purposes including tissue engineering (Wen et al., 2020), packaging (Niranjana Prabhu & Prashantha, 2018), electronics (Xiang et al., 2022), and even biodegradable drones (Wiesemüller et al., 2023). Compared to commercial rice cookies, edible cryogels are better tuneable via changes in formulation and process optimization (Zhu et al., 2024).

Conventionally, cryogels, aerogels prepared by freeze-drying, are fabricated by drying the hydrogels, and then shaped by subtractive manufacturing. To further increase the design freedom of structural materials, aerogels/cryogels can also be 3D-printed as shown in previous works (Li et al., 2017; Tetik et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2021). Extrusion-based 3D printing is emerging as a novel food processing method (Dankar et al., 2018), enabling the creation of complex designs and

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Fig. 1. Original digital designs and images of 3D-printed starch cryogel designs after freeze-drying. (a): G-code rendered images of different infill patterns at 20 % infill density (SQR: square, TRI: triangular, LIN: rectilinear, HEX: hexagon and CUB: cuboid). (b): Freeze-dried designs printed with one outer perimeter. (c): Freeze-dried designs printed with two outer perimeters.

textures. It can be used, for example, to create macroporous structures with low density and strong mechanical properties. Material can be deposited mainly along stress-bearing lines, creating large holes (or pores) in areas that do not significantly contribute to the overall strength of the structure. In this way material strength is preserved whilst the overall density is minimized (Ma et al., 2024).

Any edible material that can form a shape-stable dough is suitable for 3D printing edible components, including vegetable pastes, chocolate, cheese, pasta dough, and other starch and protein formulations (Chen et al., 2022; Chung et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2018; Rong et al., 2023; Ross et al., 2021; Schutyser et al., 2018; Va et al., 2023; Zhu et al., 2023). As one of the most abundant naturally occurring polysaccharides, starch presents itself as an inexpensive, completely digestible, and energy dense food ingredient (Tontisirin et al., 2003), that is suitable for 3D food printing (Zheng et al., 2019; Zheng et al., 2021). Once 3D-printed, materials can be solidified by removal of the residual water. Baking and air drying can be used for this, and may introduce porosity and hence lower the specific density, but deformation of the 3D-printed structures is likely to occur during this drying process, since it is operated far above the glass transition of the material (Chen et al., 2022; Phuhongsung et al., 2022; Teng et al., 2021). In a previous study, commercial puffed rice cake was used to construct an edible wing (Kwak et al., 2022). Due to their uneven surface and undesired shape, the rice cake was cut into pieces and then glued into the shape of a wing. Freeze-drying also forms porous and lightweight cryogels (Baudron et al., 2019; Zhu et al., 2024), but operates at or close to the glass transition throughout the dehydration process, and hence retains the 3D-printed structure far better. Therefore, freeze-drying as a post-processing method after 3D printing better preserves the printed structure. Thus, 3D printing and subsequent freeze-drying of starch-based formulations may directly result in lightweight, strong, and dimensionally stable edible components, without requiring any further (re)shaping steps. This makes it a suitable process to investigate the interaction between the material's properties and the large-scale, geometric product design.

Consequently, this study hypothesizes that the mechanical properties of products made of starch cryogels can be adjusted by their geometric

design. Both the infill pattern and the thickness of the outer perimeter is investigated while keeping the overall infill density constant. As an exemplary application, this is expected to enable effective design of components for various parts of an edible airframe. Therefore, starch-based inks were 3D-printed into cuboidal shapes with different infill designs, and with different outer perimeter thicknesses. The printed designs were then freeze-dried into cryogels. The 3D printable starch-based ink was developed via preliminary trials, which showed good consistency during extrusion and high shape fidelity after 3D printing and freeze-drying processes. Uniaxial compression tests were conducted to determine the mechanical properties of starch cryogel designs. The obtained stress-strain curves were analysed to obtain parameters such as Young's modulus and to create a texture map. Digital image correlation (DIC) was used to elucidate the fracture mechanics of the designs. To demonstrate the potential application of 3D-printed cryogel as a structural material for robots, a partially edible glider was designed and evaluated through simple glide flight tests.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Materials

Wheat starch was purchased from The Amazing Oriental shop (Oriental Holding Europe, Hoofddorp, the Netherlands). The moisture content of wheat starch powder was 11.28 % on a wet basis. Glycerol (Bidistilled 99.5 %) was purchased from VWR Chemicals BDH® (Radnor, PA, USA). Demineralized water was used to prepare the formulations in all experiments.

2.2. Preparation of starch-based hydrogel inks

Starch-based hydrogel ink was prepared by mixing wheat starch and glycerol with demineralized water. A recipe found to be most suitable for printing in preliminary tests was 25 % w/w wheat starch, 3 % w/w glycerol and 72 % w/w water. All ingredients were weighed before transferring to a 100 mL Schott flask. To ensure adequate mixing, starch

Table 1
Overview of 45x45x15 mm square structure designs with 20 % infill density.

Design code	Infill pattern	Perimeter count
SQR1	square grid	1
SQR2	square grid	2
TRI1	triangular	1
TRI2	triangular	2
LIN1	rectilinear	1
LIN2	rectilinear	2
HEX1	hexagon	1
HEX2	hexagon	2
CUB1	cuboid	1
CUB2	cuboid	2

suspensions were heated to 90 °C for 60 min in a stirring dry bath set at 1000 RPM (2mag AG, Munich, Germany). This resulted in a stiff, partially translucent hydrogel, which was homogenized and deaerated using a Think-ARV-310 planetary vacuum mixer (Thinky, Tokyo, Japan), at 2000 rpm and 30 kPa for 2 min. To prevent possible retrogradation which could interfere with the printability, the hydrogel was prepared in 100 g batches just prior to printing.

2.3. 3D model design

Models for 3D printing were designed in Onshape, a cloud-based computer-aided design (CAD) platform. A square structure with a width and length of 45 mm and a height of 15 mm was selected. Five infill patterns were selected for their unique design and printability (see Fig. 1). An infill density of 20 % was chosen on the assumption that it would provide satisfactory mechanical properties after freeze-drying whilst keeping the designs lightweight. For each infill pattern, the effect of the wall thickness was investigated by printing the same infill pattern but varying the outer perimeter thickness, by printing it either once or twice, from here identified a perimeter count of one or two. This resulted in ten different designs, summarized in Table 1. Examples of different types of infill patterns can be found in Appendix 1. It is noteworthy that for square and triangular patterns, the pattern of each layer was exactly the same. However, in rectilinear and hexagonal patterns, the patterns of adjacent layers were perpendicular. For example, in the sample with a rectilinear infill, every odd layer had only horizontal infill, while every even layer has only vertical infill. This resulted in samples with rectilinear and hexagonal patterns appearing denser in a top view compared to square and triangular, even though all structures had the same infill density. Additionally, a control material with 100 % infill density was fabricated by mould casting. CAD models were exported into Slic3r 1.3.0 to generate the G-code for 3D printing.

2.4. Fabrication of edible structural components

2.4.1. 3D printing

Designs were printed using the Procusini 5.0 Food 3D Printer (Procusini, Freising, Germany). A 1.2 mm TT Series Grey tapered nozzle (Nordson EFD, Ohio, USA) was used for printing to achieve good extrudability and print quality (Karyappa & Hashimoto, 2019; Zhu et al., 2022). The nozzle was attached to a custom stainless-steel cartridge with a 27 mm inner diameter and an approximate volume of 75 mL. Before printing, the cartridge was fully packed with starch hydrogel ink to minimize effects of uneven extrusion caused by air pockets (See Section 2.2). A nozzle temperature of 40 °C was chosen to delay possible starch retrogradation (Wang et al., 2015). A 1.2 mm layer height was selected, based on literature suggesting the highest print accuracy at a layer height equal to the nozzle diameter (Chen et al., 2022). Based on preliminary tests, the print speed was set to 12.5 mm/s for outer walls and 10.0 mm/s for infill. During printing process, the extrusion direction was perpendicular to the plane of the infill pattern. The ambient temperature during printing was 21 °C and relative humidity was 32 %. An overview

of the processing parameters can be found in Appendix 2. After printing, designs were immediately transferred to a freezer in sealed polyethylene bags at −18 °C for 20 h for solidification. As a reference for density determination and mechanical assessment, controls were fabricated by casting hydrogel ink into a polylactic acid (PLA) mould. The mould was fabricated using a Creality Ender 3 S1 plastic FDM printer (Creality 3D Technology, Shenzhen, China). Creality Slicer 4.8.2 was used for generating G-code. The casts were frozen in accordance with the procedure described for the printed designs. All designs including the controls were fabricated in duplicate.

2.4.2. Freeze-drying

After freezing, the printed designs were dried using a Christ Epsilon 2-10D pilot scale freeze dryer (Martin Christ GmbH, Osterode am Harz, Germany). A custom program with a drying time of 96 h was used to dry the designs into cryogels. Dried designs were stored in a glass desiccator vessel (DWK, Wertheim, Germany) before further analyses.

2.5. Characterizations of 3D-printed wheat starch cryogels

2.5.1. Moisture content analysis

The moisture content of all designs was measured using a Sartorius MA37 automated moisture analyser (Sartorius, Göttingen, Germany), which weighted and calculated the moisture content automatically. Analysis was performed at a temperature of 140 °C and at atmospheric pressure.

2.5.2. Bulk density and shrinkage rate analysis

The dimensions of the cryogels, from which the volume was calculated, were determined using digital callipers (Mitutoyo®). The bulk density of structures was calculated according to Eq. (1).

$$\rho_m = \frac{m_d}{V_d} \quad (1)$$

In which, ρ_m is the bulk density (kg/m^3), m_d is the measured mass of the design after freeze-drying (kg), and V_d is the calculated bulk volume based on the length, width, and height of the freeze-dried design (m^3).

The shrinkage rate (SR) of dried designs was calculated by comparing the dimensions of the printed designs before and after freeze-drying. This was done using an adapted shrinkage percentage formula (Chen et al., 2022):

$$\text{SR} (\%) = \frac{\Delta L + \Delta W + \Delta H}{L + W + H} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where L , W , and H are the measured length (m), width (m), and height (m) of freeze-dried designs, respectively. ΔL , ΔW , and ΔH are the difference in length (m), width (m), and height (m) between the printed structure and the structure after drying.

2.5.3. Texture analysis

Compression tests were performed using an Instron® 68TM-5 texture analyser, equipped with a 50 mm round compression plate and a 2 kN load cell (Instron, Norwood, Massachusetts, USA). The designs were placed with the solid shell side in parallel to the horizontal support surface. A pre-test speed of 20 mm/s with a trigger force of 0.05 N was used. Designs were compressed at 2.5 mm/s. The test was stopped when designs reached 15 % compressive strain or when the force decreased to 80 % of the peak force. The compressive stress σ (Pa) was calculated by dividing the measured compressive force by the contact area between the sample and the upper plate using Eq. (3). The measured strain ε (%) was calculated using Eq. (4).

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{WL} \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta H}{H} \quad (4)$$

In which F is the compressive force (N), W is the measured width of the rectangular design (m), L is the measured length (m), ΔH is the measured difference in height before and during compression (m), and H is the measured height (m).

The Young's modulus E (Pa) was calculated using the slope of the linear region of the obtained compression curves according to Eq. (5).

$$E = \frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta\varepsilon} \quad (5)$$

In which, $\frac{\Delta\sigma}{\Delta\varepsilon}$ (Pa) is the slope of the linear region of the compression curve.

The fracture strength (σ_{max}) was measured by finding the global maximum of the plotted stress-strain curves. The fracture strain (ε_{max}) was defined as the strain at which macroscopic failure/fracture occurred.

The specific modulus was calculated according to Eq. (6).

$$\phi = \frac{E}{\rho} \quad (6)$$

In which, ϕ (J/kg) is the calculated specific modulus, E is the calculated Young's modulus (Pa) and ρ is the calculated density (kg/m^3). All measurements were done in duplicate and averaged.

2.5.4. Digital image correlation

Compression tests were recorded with a Sony FDR-AX53 video camera (Sony Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) equipped with a Zeiss Vario-Sonnar T 2.0/4.4–88 lens (Carl Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany). The test area was illuminated using two Ledgo E268C LED lights at 5000 K (Ledgo, Shantou, China).

Before compression, a black speckle pattern was applied (on the side with bare infill pattern). Randomly distributed black speckles with a total surface coverage of approximately 50 % were applied with a 0.5 mm permanent marker. Individual frames from the obtained videos were exported as PNG images using VLC media player 3.0.20 (VideoLAN, Paris, France). For each design, an image at 0 % strain was used as the reference. Due to the relative complexity and inhomogeneity of the structures, the region of interest (ROI) was manually selected using Adobe Photoshop CC (Adobe, San Jose, California) and imported into Ncorr 1.2 (Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, Georgia) for analysis. The region of interest (ROI) selection was created by Adobe® Photoshop® software.

Subsequent frames from the recorded videos were used for digital image correlation. The reference image was compared to the image just before measured fracture stress for DIC analysis of each design.

A desktop computer with an 8-core processor (AMD, Santa Clara, California), enabled multi-thread correlation computation with placement of 8 seeds. Seeds were placed homogeneously throughout the ROI according to the Ncorr 1.2 user manual (Blaber & Antoniou, 2017). The unit conversion between pixels and millimetres was based on a calibration image of a 40×40 mm square imported into Ncorr 1.2. Other parameters were selected in consultation with the Ncorr 1.2 user manual and based on preliminary tests. The parameters are summarized in Appendix 3.

DIC was done in both the horizontal and vertical directions. Ncorr 1.2 used DIC to calculate the $U(x, y)$ and $V(x, y)$ displacement fields of the previously mentioned subsets. In essence, the U -displacement field represents local deformation in the horizontal (x) direction (i.e. parallel to the support platform), whereas the V -displacement field represents vertical (y) deformation (i.e. perpendicular to the support platform). To produce strain fields, DIC programs like Ncorr use principles of continuum mechanics to calculate Green-Lagrangian strain tensor components ε_{xx} and ε_{yy} , and these are equivalent to the horizontal strain along the horizontal (x) and (y) axis. In other words, a heatmap of the strain

distribution describes the relative expansion or contraction of small regions of the material during compression. However, it was determined that the vertical direction plots did not reveal additional insights about the deformation behaviour and were therefore excluded from the results & discussion section for brevity. Following DIC computation, the images containing heat maps of the deformation (U displacement) and relative horizontal strain distribution (ε_{xx}) in the structures were used for analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of 3D-printed wheat starch cryogels

The 3D-printed and freeze-dried cryogels showed acceptable shape fidelity with no obvious fractures or deformations, based on visual observation and calliper measurements. A previous study has shown 3D printing of wheat starch gels resulted in accurate and good quality printing, indicating its suitability to be used as edible ink (Zheng et al., 2021). In this study, the composition of the printable ink containing wheat starch, water and glycerol was optimized via preliminary trials, which was 3D-printed into structures with good shape fidelity. In addition, introducing macropores in 3D-printed structures (i.e. low infill density of 20 % resulted in a hollow structure with increased surface area) helped limit structural abnormality of the cryogels (e.g. crack formation, bending) after freeze-drying, by ensuring more homogenous drying (Zhu et al., 2024). However, the designs with square and cubic infill patterns still exhibited minor visible print defects (see Fig. 1. SQR & CUB), due to the overhangs in the designed structure. The viscoelastic nature of the starch hydrogel ink caused the extruded filaments in the lower layers to stretch and deform under the weight of the subsequent layers. This indicates that to improve the 3D printing performance of starch hydrogels, it is recommended to avoid complex three-dimensional structures to reduce the impact of overhang deformation during printing. This can be achieved by opting for simple triangular, square, or hexagonal patterns.

The residual moisture content, shrinkage rate and bulk density of freeze-dried cryogels are reported in Appendix 4. All cryogel designs exhibited similar residual moisture content (4.93 ± 0.99 % w/w), which is acceptable for dry food products such as baked cookies (Martinez et al., 2024). Since the residual moisture content of the designs was similar, it was assumed that it did not cause significant differences in mechanical properties between infill patterns. The shrinkage rate of the designs was also found to be consistent, at 7.47 ± 0.48 %, similar to values in other studies (Baudron et al., 2019; Derossi et al., 2021; Zhu, 2019; Zhu et al., 2024). The uniform shrinkage rate allows the desired dimensions of cryogel components to be pre-determined by scaling the dimensions of the printed hydrogel.

With a constant infill density of 20 %, the measured bulk density of the structures varied strongly (157.37 ± 22.39 kg/m^3). For instance, the more complex hexagonal pattern showed a higher bulk density than the simpler square pattern, and the bulk density of designs with a 20 % infill pattern was 38–50 % of that of the moulded control (which can be regarded as 100 % infill). This indicates that there was over-extrusion of the material during 3D printing, i.e. the width of the extruded line exceeded the preset value. This is a well-known limitation of the Slic3er software, which causes variation in the mass of extruded material depending on the selected infill pattern, especially at low infill densities (Ravi, 2020). Besides, the bulk density also depends on the infill patterns. A pattern with many curves, such as hexagon, exhibits a higher extrusion rate than a simple structure, such as a square. During extrusion-based 3D printing, over-extrusion was more likely to occur at the start/stop points, which results in an increase of the total mass of the printed designs, and thus its bulk density. This study did not focus on how infill densities and patterns influence the bulk density of printed structures. To achieve a desired bulk density for a specific pattern design, it may be more useful to adjust parameters in the slicing software

Fig. 2. The stress-strain curve of 3D-printed cryogels with different infill designs (SQR: square, TRI: triangular, LIN: rectilinear, HEX: hexagon and CUB: cuboid). (a). Designs with square and linear patterns. (b). Designs with triangular and hexagonal patterns. (c). Designs with cuboidal and control group. The dashed line represents designs with 1 outer perimeter, while the solid line represents designs with 2 outer perimeters. Arrows indicate the selected fracture point.

and introduce computer vision and feedforward nozzle motion control (Ma et al., 2023).

3.2. Effects of geometric parameters on mechanical properties

3.2.1. Fracture behaviours as indicated by stress-strain curves

The mechanical properties of cryogels with different geometric parameters were characterized by texture analysis which resulted in different stress-strain curves (see Fig. 2). To better compare the compression stress-strain curve of cryogels with different patterns, the designs were categorized into three groups. The first group has square and linear patterns (see also Fig. 1): these two infill patterns showed printed lines that are parallel or perpendicular to the direction of compression. The second group consists of triangular and hexagonal patterns which added diagonal supports. The third group consists of cuboidal structures with more complex 3D structures and the moulded control as a reference.

Fig. 2a shows that the thickness of the outer perimeter has a significant impact on the compression curve of the cryogels with LIN and SQR infills. With only one printed layer as outer perimeter, the curve did not exhibit a sharp fracture point but resembled a yield point instead. When increasing the number of outer perimeter layers to two, both infill patterns showed an increased fracture stress and a reduced fracture strain and showed a distinct fracture behaviour and some localized fracture points.

With only one outer perimeter print layer, the outer wall and the infill structures had the same thickness, resulting in similar strength against deformation. As the compression strain increased, the compression stress kept on increasing until a ‘plateau’ was reached.

Afterwards, the structures fractured as indicated by the shape decrease of compression stress. With two outer perimeters, the outer wall was thicker than the infill structures, causing the infill lines (i.e. the weaker spots) to fracture first during compression. As the compression strain increased, those broken fragments of the infills became more and more densely packed, leading to multiple fracture events as indicated by multiple peaks in compressions stress (Derossi et al., 2021; Gibson, 2003). In addition, due to the more densely printed lines that were perpendicular to the direction of compression, the linear (LIN) pattern has a higher fracture stress and a lower fracture strain at the first fracture point compared to the square (SQR) pattern. This suggests that the mechanical strength of the rectilinear infill patterns can be tuned by adjusting the infill density and how the printed lines are distributed in the structures.

Interestingly, when changing the infill patterns to hexagonal (HEX) and triangular (TRI) (i.e. adding diagonal supports), designs with only one outer perimeter exhibited a sharp fracture point which was not seen with the SQR and LIN designs (see Figs. 2a & 2b), showing a higher structural rigidity. During compression, the diagonal printed lines redistributed the load which helped to brace the structure and resulted in reduced fracture strain and a more abrupt and distinct fracture point. By providing additional pathways for stress distribution using the HEX pattern, the diagonal supports increase the overall strength and stiffness of the structure (i.e. increased Young’s modulus, see Fig. 3a).

Furthermore, increasing the thickness (number of printed perimeters) of the outer perimeters resulted in a decrease of the fracture strain for both the TRI and HEX designs, making the structures more brittle. The fracture stress of the TRI design significantly increased when two outer perimeter was used, which was however not seen in the HEX design

Fig. 3. Comparing mechanical properties of 3D-printed cryogels with different geometrical designs (SQR: square, TRI: triangular, LIN: rectilinear, HEX: hexagon and CUB: cuboid; number of outer perimeters is indicated by value 1 or 2). (a): Ashby plot of Young’s modulus and bulk density. (b): Texture map of fracture stress and strain. (c): Specific modulus, sorted in ascending order. Numerical values of all plots can be found in Appendix 5.

Fig. 4. DIC method of U displacement analysis (SQR: square, TRI: triangular, HEX: hexagon and CUB: cuboid). In the colour bar on the right side, '+' represents displacement to the right, '-' represents displacement to the left, the relative extent of deformation is indicated by different colours. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

(Fig. 2b). This could be because HEX design exhibited a more uniform structure, which resulted in a more even distribution of stress across all structures. As a result, the number of outer perimeters has little impact on the fracture stress of the HEX designs.

Moreover, it can be observed that the moulded control exhibited numerous localized fracture points (Fig. 2c) with the highest fracture stress exceeding the value of 1400 kPa. The moulded control was freeze-dried from a bulk hydrogel. During freezing, ice crystals form and are subsequently removed from the matrix via sublimation, resulting in a lightweight porous structure. The pores in the structures can be seen as defects in the bulk structure, which do not contribute to the strength of the structure during compression and cause multiple peaks in the stress-strain curve. Therefore, the moulding method is not recommended for fabricating cryogel structures for applications that require mechanical strength. Instead, cryogels produced through 3D printing can be designed with macroporous structures which promote uniform drying and help avoid such defects. However, lines printed with cuboidal infill patterns differed in the printing direction, causing a relatively low printing precision, shape fidelity and stability after drying. The uneven distributed internal structures of the CUB design also introduced numerous small cracks after drying, resulting in fracture behaviour similar to that of the control during compression.

3.2.2. Comparing different geometric designs

The relationship between the Young's modulus and the measured density of the 3D-printed cryogels is visualized in Fig. 3a. Comparison between the design groups with different outer perimeters shows that an increase in wall thickness generally leads to increased stiffness and density. Designs with two outer perimeter lines (group with red background) exhibited a higher Young's modulus and bulk density than those with one perimeter line (group with blue background). When comparing the different perimeter settings for the same infill pattern, the largest differences are observed with triangular and square infill patterns, with an increase of $168 \pm 27\%$ and $134 \pm 28\%$, indicating that the perimeter settings have a significant impact on their stiffness. Detailed values can be found in the appendix 5.

A similar trend was observed for the fracture stress and strain of the designs: an increase in fracture stress was seen for all infill patterns with two outer perimeters (see Fig. 3b). However, the designs with one outer perimeter line show higher strain at fracture stress, which indicates higher ductility. In several cases, this also led to a higher capacity to absorb energy before yielding. The details will be discussed later.

For aerospace applications in which minimum structural weight is required, the specific modulus can be used to evaluate the stiffness of the materials at the same bulk density. Fig. 3c confirms that a thicker outer perimeter of the cryogel leads to an increase in compressive stiffness,

which is not caused merely by a higher measured density. The specific modulus (stiffness-to-weight ratio) is confirmed to be higher for all designs with two perimeter lines compared to the same infill patterns with one perimeter line. The highest specific modulus (134.34 ± 1.70 kJ/kg) is observed for TRI2. This design has a specific modulus that is over 51 % larger than the weakest design with two perimeter lines (CUB2). This indicates that the triangular design is best suited for structures that need to be lightweight yet stiff, such as the ribs of an aircraft wing.

Several conclusions can be drawn from these findings. Firstly, structures with one outer perimeter lines are more ductile and less stiff than those with two perimeter lines. Secondly, the infill pattern design indeed affects the mechanical properties of the printed starch cryogel structures at the same measured density. Infill patterns such as linear and square with only horizontal and vertical structures are more ductile, while structures with diagonal supports such as triangular and hexagon are stiffer.

The layer thickness, infill pattern, infill density, shell thickness, and build orientation have the most influence on the properties (Qamar Tanveer et al., 2022). In most studies, the testing direction for textural analysis is the same as the build orientation, being perpendicular to the infill pattern surface (Aloyaydi et al., 2020; Derossi et al., 2020; Mantihal et al., 2019b). This will result in a structure that has no overhang in the direction of the load. Therefore, parameters such as infill density and layer thickness have the most effects. In this study, the testing direction was perpendicular to the build orientation. This enables printing of taller and more slender structures, which renders the shell thickness (perimeter settings) and the infill pattern the most influential parameters.

3.3. Fracture mechanics of the different geometric 3D-printed designs

To better understand the fracture mechanics of cryogels during compression, images just before the structures fractured were analysed using the DIC method. Two types of analyses were done, namely U displacement and relative horizontal strain (ϵ_{xx}). The CUB design had a complex three-dimensional internal structure and the DIC method essentially only analyses 2D projections of the front surface. Therefore, the DIC images of the CUB design are in fact less informative as compared to the results of other designs, which will not be discussed intensively here. They are however added for the interest of the readers.

U displacement analysis follows the horizontal displacement of each point in the design during the compression test (Fig. 4). It indicates the extent of deformation under stress. Since the linear and square printed patterns exhibited very similar behaviour, only the results of the square infill pattern are shown. Fig. 4 shows that the U displacement values for the square infill patterns were fairly similar when looking at the lines

Fig. 5. DIC method of ϵ_{xx} analysis (SQR: square, TRI: triangular, HEX: hexagon and CUB: cuboid). In the colour bar on the right side, '+' represents the structure is in a state of elongation, and '-' represents the structure is in a state of compression, the relative value of the horizontal strain is indicated by different colours. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

parallel to the direction of compression. The middle part of the structure showed displacements towards the right side as indicated by the red/yellow colours in the heatmap. This horizontal displacement of structure during compression led to yielding instead of fracturing, and larger fracture strain values (See Figs. 2a & 4 SQR), In contrast, after introducing diagonal supports (Fig. 4 TRI & HEX), the middle part of the structure showed different directions of displacement, as indicated by a gradual change in colour from blue to red in the horizontal direction. The different displacement directions at each point in the horizontal direction are more likely to cause fracture in the middle of the structure during compression tests.

The ϵ_{xx} plot explains the relative horizontal strain between each point of the design during the compression test (Fig. 5). A positive ϵ_{xx} value indicates elongation while a negative ϵ_{xx} value indicates compression. Fig. 5 shows that the SQR designs were overall compressed with only a few vertical spots under tension. This means that the horizontal beams experienced minimal strain, and the vertical beams primarily contributed to the strength of the structures during compression and deformed the most. This suggests inefficient use of the material for structural strength. However, after adding diagonal supports (TRI & HEX patterns), the designs exhibited a wider range of relative horizontal strains as indicated by the uneven colour distribution across the structures. A larger positive ϵ_{xx} indicates that the structure deforms more under stress, which was observed in the middle part of the TRI & HEX structures just before fracture. This is in line with what was seen in the U displacement analysis: fracture of TRI and HEX structures first occurs in the middle of the design during compression. It also shows that these structures experience significant forces during the compression test and can withstand higher stress and exhibit a higher Young's modulus. This agrees with findings from another study that patterns with more bonding zones are tougher (Mantihal et al., 2019a).

The fracture behaviour of the TRI design was the most affected by the perimeter thickness. The CUB designs had many random distributed dark red/blue locations, indicating that large cracks had already formed before the fracture finally took place. This consistent with the stress-strain curve analysis in the previous section. To summarize, based on DIC and stress-strain curve analyses, we can better understand how infill pattern and perimeter setting affects the fracture mechanics of cryogel structures. This understanding can be used to provide design guidelines of 3D-printed starch cryogels with different mechanical performance.

3.4. Design guideline and potential applications of 3D-printed edible cryogels

We demonstrated that the mechanical properties wheat starch cryogels can be tuned (e.g. varying from ductile to stiff) by changing the geometrical design of 3D-printed structures (i.e. infill pattern and number of outer perimeter) while keeping the ink composition and infill density the same. The impact of geometry on the mechanical performance of 3D-printed cryogels is visualized in Fig. 6 which may serve as design guideline of 3D-printed cryogels as a structural material. Different combinations of structural designs give different properties. In brief, structures with one outer perimeter line were more ductile than those with two outer perimeter lines. With one outer perimeter line, a square infill design resulted in a lightweight structure while a linear infill design led to higher energy absorption ability. With two outer perimeter lines, a hexagonal infill design distributes stresses evenly during compression while a triangular design gives the highest specific modulus. Depending on the application scenarios of this kind of material, the proper geometry can be selected. A cuboidal infill gives a more complex fracture behaviour as compared to others. It is noteworthy that the mechanical performance of cryogels is also influenced by the

Fig. 6. A map for guiding the design of 3D-printed cryogel geometries based on mechanical requirements and bulk density.

Fig. 7. Fabrication and flight test of a partially edible glider. (a) CAD design of the glider. White components are starch cryogels, light brown components are balsa wood. (b) Constructed concept glider with prototype wings and a starch cryogel nose cone. (c) A flight test of partially edible glider. The glider was thrown from the second floor, and the gliding distance was approximately 25 m. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

formulation design (Zhu et al., 2024). Future studies could focus on investigating the influences of the chemical composition of edible inks (e.g. use of different starch sources and/or incorporation of additives) (Zou & Budtova, 2021) on the 3D printing and freeze-drying processes and the properties of the obtained structures. Moreover, more comprehensive analyses on starch hydrogels/cryogels are recommended for future work especially when more complex formulations are used, including chemical properties analysis using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) and microstructure analysis (e.g. using scanning electron microscope) (Boccia et al., 2024; Jiang et al., 2023). By combining the formulation design and the structural design, 3D printing is a versatile method to create edible structural materials that have similar or even superior material properties compared to conventional non-edible engineering materials.

We demonstrate the design principles with the use of 3D-printed cryogels as structural components in an unpowered glider. In general, gliders need to be lightweight and strong. Different parts of the glider may have different design requirements due to their specific functional demands (see Fig. 7). Therefore, the triangular infill pattern with two outer perimeter lines was selected for printing the wing ribs due to its high specific modulus ensuring high stiffness at low density. The rectilinear infill pattern with one outer perimeter was selected for printing the nose cone, as an anti-collision part due to its higher ductility. The ribs were connected using spruce and balsa wood spars, to complete the construction. Individual parts were then bonded with non-toxic polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) glue. The wing was covered with commercially available starch-based edible paper. The prototype of this edible glider is shown in Fig. 7. The production process and design parameters are detailed in Appendices 6 and 7.

The completed wing weighed just 106.1 g thanks to its low density (55.6 kg/m^3). The calculated calorie content of the edible parts was approximately 265 kcal, which was close to the calorie content of 100 g of whole grain bread. The individual cryogel ribs have a mass of 2.80 g with a measured density of 130.7 kg/m^3 . Compared to an EPP foam wing, it has a lower density and a higher stiffness. In the future, a fully edible glider for rescue missions may be created by replacing the spruce and balsa beams with edible materials.

4. Conclusion

The aim of this work was to investigate the impact of structural design on the mechanical performance of 3D-printed wheat starch

cryogels. Uniaxial compression and DIC strain analysis showed that a wide range of mechanical and material properties can be obtained by simply changing the geometry of starch cryogels. Among the structural designs evaluated, a triangular infill pattern with two outer perimeter lines gave the highest specific modulus, which is desirable for applications such as in edible airframes. A rectilinear infill pattern gives the best energy-absorbing characteristics. As a demonstration, a partially edible unpowered glider, which showed stable gliding performance during a flight test, was assembled using 3D-printed starch cryogels as the main structural material. Our work contributes to a better understanding of the fracture mechanics of 3D-printed edible structures, and apart from novel applications like gliders, could also be used to design 3D-printed snacks with desirable texture and nutritional properties.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ruihao Zhu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jáchym Jarkulisch:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Maarten A.I. Schutyser:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Remko M. Boom:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Lu Zhang:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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